

Optimised Hybrid Integrated Renewable Energy System

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Abstract: A hybrid integrated renewable energy system for an isolated small community, where grid extension is considered uneconomical. This paper proposed cost optimization through dynamic matching between load and proper equipment sizing. The Matlab based computer program developed for determining the most cost effective energy source to supply required load any given time of the day. Integrated system based on green energy utilization and rural electricity development.

Keywords: MATLAB programming, Hybrid renewable system

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy sources are expected to contribute substantially towards meeting rapidly increasing global energy demand because they are abundant and freely available, virtually pollution free and have comparatively low maintenance costs. Renewable energy based power generation has received considerable attention in recent years in many countries of the world. In the remote isolated area and off grid communities such as rural area lying remotely renewable energy sources are usually the main sources of power supply. In india many rural area remotely located here grid extension is cost effective as compare to using renewable energy sources available. However, along the mid-west area also have substantially levels of wind energy that can be harnessed for electrification. Therefore in such area, solar and wind energy based systems can be used to harness both forms of energy for the electrification of households remote from the grid. Hybrid system consists of two or more energy systems, an energy storage system, power conditioning equipment and a controller. Rural load characterized by low power factor, which has negative influence on plant operating cost effective supply them from the grid. In this case, renewable energy sources become economically the best alternatives despite having comparatively high installation costs. The Costs can be minimized by effectively matching sources and load characteristics. The technical analysis involves a study of sources and load characteristics, design and optimization. In the study three types of renewable energy sources considered were small hydro, wind and PV solar system.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 **STUDY AREA:** The remote rural area for the study was kanteri in district Dhar Madhya Pradesh India the area comprises of hilly and fertile area under forest with scattered households. This village divided three zones of clusters of village and only 30% area of the total villages are electrified. The literacy percentage of village 20% women and 65% men. The area has been considered by Urja Vikas Nigam, Bhopal (MP) to be remote and not economically viable for electrification by grid extension. It has satisfactory sunshine, low moderate wind speed and a few, mainly seasonal stream feeding in to that area.

Proposed layout for this side shown in figure:-

Fig. 1

2.2 INFORMATION ACQUIREMENT:

A questionnaire was developed for the purpose of conducting a survey to determine the load demand. Apart from the Panchayat, school, and a few households, which have supply systems, no other household or building is electrified. So for the majority of the respondents, the obtained data was on perceived demand. The level and pattern of demand were evaluated on the basis of appliances, which the customer would own, and their pattern of use. The data on potentials of the three types of renewable energy sources considered was obtained from Urja Vikas Nigam, Bhopal (MP) and the meteorological & hydrological maps for the area. It was obtained as insolation levels, wind speeds as well as stream discharge rates and heads. Additional data was obtained from suppliers and users of RE systems for the purpose of creating a data base on unit costs.

2.3 RESOURCES ESTIMATION

A MATLAB Ver 2009a computer program was developed to determine the most cost effective HRE source for given load conditions, taking into account both economic and technical factors. The potential output power and unit cost of each of the three sources were evaluated using the following equations:

SMALL HYDRO SUBSYSTEM:-

A small hydropower generating unit is identified as a power supply that feeds a distant or a local load from a small hydroelectric source, which could either be run-of river, or have a small impoundment. Small hydro installations are designed for capacity ranges between 300kW and 30 MW. Mini hydro is sometimes designated as ranging from 100kW to 300kW. Micro hydro units are between 10kW to 100kW. Below 10kW capacity can also be labeled as micro hydro (Pico hydro has also been used). This paper however utilizes “small hydro” as an encompassing term for representing micro, mini, and small hydro units.

$$P_{shp} = K \cdot Q \cdot H \cdot G_{shp} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:-

- Pshp = Power from mini hydro in kW
- Q = flow rate in m³/s - -
- Gshp= turbine efficiency
- H = effective head in m
- K is constant including water density and the acceleration due to gravity

PV SUBSYSTEM:-

The instantaneous electric energy generated by a PV cell depends on several cell parameters and on variable environment conditions such as insolation and temperature.

Its electric behavior may be simply modeled by a nonlinear current source connected in series with the intrinsic cell series resistance.

$$P_{pv} = G \cdot A \cdot G_{pv} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:-

- PP. = power from solar in kW
- G = solar irradiance in kW/m²
- A = panel area in m², G_{pv} = efficiency

WIND SUBSYSTEM:-

The model considers some identical wind turbine generators, and corrections about the power developed with reference to variations of the air density, and the position of the wind turbine in the field are included. In fact, the energy production of identical machines is normally different due to local effects. The aerodynamic power generated by the wind turbine is proportional to

$$P_{wtg} = A_r \cdot k \cdot V^3 \cdot G_{ef} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where:-

- Pwtg = power from wind turbine generator in kW
- A_r = area of rotor blades in m²
- V = wind speed in m/s
- G_{ef}= effective efficiency

$$C_u = LCC / (A_f \cdot C_d \cdot 365) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:-

- C_u= unit cost in R/kW
- A_f = annualisation factor= $\frac{\{(1+i)^n - 1\}}{i \cdot (1+i)^n}$
- i = interest rate and n = number of years
- LCC = life cycle cost in R
- C_d = demand in kW

- Ppv = PV Power,
- Pwtg = Wind Turbine Generator Power,
- Pchs = Hybrid Power,
- Cchs = cost of hybrid system,
- Cinst = insolation cost,
- Cbatt = batteries cost
- Cman = maintenance cost
- Celect = other electrical (devices) system related

The unit cost was evaluated on the assumption that the load is for the whole year.

$$C_p = P_o * C_u \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where:

- CP = power cost in Rs.
- Po = unit output power in kW (as calculated using equations (1) to (3)).

The parameters required for the execution of the program were: time of day (for which the user wishes to evaluate power requirement), average daily wind speed (m/s), flow rate (m3/s) and insolation level (kWh/m2). Each of the sources was treated individually, that is, unavailability of one did not hinder the evaluation of the other sources. The program calculated the unit cost of each of the identified sources, identified the most cost effective source and the maximum power available from this source. In the modeling of PV solar sources, storage facilities (i.e. batteries) were also considered. The sizing of the battery was made to be an input parameter, which the user can specify. The results of the program are stored in a separate file, which can be accessed any time. These results remain unchanged as long as the program is not executed again. So every time the program is executed, the old results are overwritten by the latest results. This feature is added to the program to allow the user to be able to study the results

carefully. The program can be adapted for application in any area.

III. DISCUSSION

The results shown in Table 1 are for specified input parameters, which can vary for individual customers, as well as, from area to area. The reliability of the evaluated unit costs depends on the accuracy of data acquired on demand patterns, assessed potential and assumed load factors of the RE sources. The annual load factor is considered to be one of the main factors for determining the investment cost amortization component of supplied energy. Due to the intermittent nature of the renewable energy sources, their annual load factors, especially for stand-alone systems, are usually low. Typical mean values are 2.5% for PV sources, 22.5% for wind sources and 75% for small-hydro sources. The program has been developed to take care of such variations, and can therefore, be the program can also be adapted for real time control of hybrid systems, through an inter-phase with an online data acquisition system for load monitoring. Information on actual or forecast load data can be processed together with stored data on the characteristics of the hybrid systems component sources, to determine the optimum operating condition.

IV. CONCLUSION

Given the fact that a hybrid energy system consisting two or more renewable energy sources has the advantage of stability, the objective of the electrification at the study area can be achieved by making use of wind, solar, micro hydro and biomass with diesel generator. The information about local wind, solar, micro hydro and biomass indicates that a feasible hybrid energy system can be planned, modeled and designed for the above purpose. The collected data of the various energy sources was analyzed in order to plan for the structure of the system. The developed program simplifies the task of determining the most cost effective renewable source to supply a given load, and is, therefore, a useful tool in systems load sizing. Further work is being carried to improve the program so that it can also be used as an online power monitoring and control system for hybrid systems. By feeding in real time data on load demand, the program can determine the most cost-effective source to supply a given load. For areas where grid supply is an option, the program can also be used to evaluate both the supplier and customer costs.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Drd.Ing. Ionela NEGREA, "Life cycle cost method calculation for a small hybrid system PV-Wind" Volume VI (XVI), 2007, Fascicle of Management and Technological Engineering,
- [2] Jan T. Bialasiewicz, "Renewable Energy Systems with Photovoltaic Power Generators: Operation

and Modeling” IEEE transaction on industrial electronics, Vol.55, no.7 july-2008.

[3] Goodarz Ghanavati, “Dynamic Simulation of a Wind Fuel Cell hybrid Power Generation System” IEEE 2009.

[4] Ajay gupta, “Optimized Application of hybrid renewable energy system in rural electrification”, Proceedings of India International Conference on Power Electronics IIIT Rookies 2006 IEEE

[5] N.M.Ijumba, “Optimized application of renewable energy sources in rural electrification” 1999, IEEE.

[6] <http://www.mp.renewable.nic.in/minih.html>

Table 1: Sample program output

The program was executed at different loading conditions with other parameters fixed, i.e. flow rate, wind speed and irradiance.

Annualisation factor	8.51
Time of day (evaluation)	14.00 H
Flow rate (m ³ /s)	2.21
Wind speed (m ² /s)	7.0
Irradiation (KWh/m ²)	0.625

Results at loading- 200 KW				Results at loading- 250 KW		
S. No	Sources	Power O/P (KW)	Cost/unit (Rs/KW)	Sources	Power O/P (KW)	Cost/unit (Rs/KW)
1	SHP Power	221.1370	2.8975	SHP Power	221.1370	2.3180
2	PV Power	6.4800	2.0926	PV Power	6.4800	1.6741
3	WTG Power	61.8767	1.6097	WTG Power	61.8767	1.2878

Loading:-

- Total potential is : 289.5 KW
- Cost effective source o/p is: 753.90 Rs.
- Percentage load supplied by cheapest source is : 30.94
- Balance obtains from next available cheapest source.

Loading:-

- Total potential is : 289.5 KW
- Cost effective source o/p is: 603.123 Rs.
- Percentage load supplied by cheapest source is : 24.75
- Balance obtains from next available cheapest source.

Flow chart for HIREES

Flow chart for HIREES